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**Religion and Development:
Interdisciplinary Perspectives**

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Contents

Editorial	3
Authentic Development: Some Gandhian Criteria <i>Subhash Anand</i>	5
Hinduism and Development <i>T K John, SJ</i>	27
Folk/Subaltern Religion and Development <i>James Ponnaiah</i>	51
Cultivating a Global Mentality: Virtue Ethics for an Age of Globalization <i>Keith D'Souza SJ</i>	69
The Voice of the Marginal and the Poor: Responsibility as the Basic Concept for Development Ethics in the Footsteps of Emmanuel Levinas <i>Roger Burggraeve SVD</i>	91
The Understanding of Development in the Documents of the Magisterium <i>Jose Thayil SJ</i>	113
Development as Quasi-Religious: A Critical Appraisal <i>Gnana Patrick</i>	126
Faith, Reason and the University: Reflections on a Recent Address of the Pope <i>Julian Saldanha SJ</i>	145
Effects of Sexual Abuse: Data from Clinical Experience <i>Jose Parappully SDB</i>	155
Book Review	164

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In recent years there has been a renewed interest in the role of religion in the course of development and its ethics within the context of globalization and the emerging world order. The latest concepts in developmental theories such as self-cultivation, the face of the other, etc., bring the agenda of development close to the question of religion. Some authors think of development itself as quasi-religious. It is against this background that this issue of *Jnanadeepa* seeks to bring both religion and development together for a meaningful dialogue between the two in the global world of today.

There are three articles in this issue which deal with Indian perspectives on religion and development. The first seeks to put forward some Gandhian criteria for authentic development. The author feels that well-being is an experience of integration. He believes that Satya should be the goal of development; that Ahimsa should be its ethos; that Svadeshi offers the resources for development; and that Swaraj creates the right environment for development. The second discusses the relationship between Hinduism and development. After pointing out some of the problems involved in the discussion of this issue, the author tries to clarify the concept of development. To his mind development is the dynamic process of the actualization of a dream, a journey from one situation to another, a transformation of something into something. Development is concerned about transforming the lives of the people, not just transforming economies. Hinduism has made a remarkable contribution to the development of a great civilization. But at a particular point in time a certain degree of closure of mind and its exploration intervened which has adversely affected the growth of human persons and the development of society. The third deals with folk/subaltern religion and development. Folk religions can help to clarify the concept of development and release forces that can promote holistic development. Such religions can function as a subaltern agency to defy the oppressive social order, to negotiate a new egalitarian social identity and restore the human dignity of the oppressed. They can also promote a type of development which is eco-friendly.

Included in this issue are three articles which discuss the ethical dimension of development. The first deals with development in the social

teaching of the Church. The author points out that the Church's understanding of development has undergone change. While the promotion of development in underdeveloped nations is primarily the responsibility of each such nation, the more advanced countries should come to their aid. The Church also calls attention to the need for moral development along with economic and social development. The second deals with the need to cultivate a global mentality in the contemporary world. This is an essay in virtue ethics applied to the phenomenon of globalization and social development, guided by the role and influence of religion. Dialogical pluralism, creative visualization, collaborative solidarity, transnational responsibility and proactive optimism are some of the virtues the article advocates. The third seeks to broaden and deepen development ethics with the thought of Emmanuel Levinas. Responsibility is the basic concept of development ethics. While we should feel responsible for the poor and the marginalized we should see to it that our altruism does not promote egocentrism in the poor. We are responsible for the responsibility of the poor and the marginalized for others.

There is an article in this issue which discusses some of the features of development which make it quasi-religious. It points out that new approaches to development that are emerging today need to be supported by new forms of religious intervention. Liberation theology is an example of the critical intervention of religion in societal transformation. Another article deals with the role of the Christian Church in the development of Goa. There has been a progressive abandonment of the Portuguese legacy. The post-colonial Church in Goa has made a renewed commitment to the promotion of the development of the State and expressed its readiness to be an active partner in the collaborative effort for regeneration. The Church believes that it is her sacred duty towards humanity to help in the integral development of the human person and the human society. This is certainly a progressive step.

Included in this issue are two articles which are not connected with its main theme. The first offers some critical reflections on a recent address of the Pope on Faith, Reason and the University. The second discusses the data from clinical experience on the effects of sexual abuse.

It is our fond hope that this issue of *Jnanadeepa* will promote a serious reflection on religion and development which will lead to new approaches to the process of personal and societal development.

James Ponnaiah & Kuruvilla Pandikattu
Guest Editors